

National Education Policy 2020- A Roadmap with Futuristic Vision

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ABSTRACT

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) is formulated to revamp education system and lay down road map for new India. This policy is aligned to the 2030 agenda for sustainable development and aims to transform India into a vibrant knowledge society. The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) must evolve to make education more experiential, holistic, integrated, inquiry-driven, discovery-oriented learner-centered, discussion-based, flexible and enjoyable. The policy envisions imaginative and flexible curricular structures to enable creative combinations of disciplines for study, that would offer multiple entry and exist points, thus, removing currently prevalent rigid boundaries and creating new possibilities for life-long learning and centrally involves critical and interdisciplinary thinking. NEP 2020 built on the foundational pillars of Access, Equity, Quality, Affordability and Accountability to meet the challenges of 21st Century. NEP2020 is largely a very progressive document, with a firm grasp on the current socio-economic landscape and the prospect to meet future challenges. If implemented properly; then it has got everything to make India global hub in education by 2030.

KEYWORDS: Access, Equity, Quality, Affordability and Accountability

The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020), which was approved by the Union Cabinet of India on 29 July 2020, outlines the vision of India's new education system. The new policy replaces the previous National Policy on Education, 1986 (Hindustan Times, 2020). The policy is a comprehensive framework for elementary education to higher education as well as vocational training in both rural and urban India. The policy aims to transform India's education system by 2021. The language policy in NEP is a broad guideline and advisory in nature; and it is up to the states, institutions, and schools to decide on the implementation. The NEP 2020 enacts numerous changes in India's education policy. It aims to increase state expenditure on education from around 4% to 6% of the GDP as soon as possible.

As students play a very important role in nation building and are considered the future leaders of a civilized human society. They are the hope of a progressive sustainable society. At the same time they are most vulnerable section of our society. Educationist guardians teachers societal policy maker

How to cite this paper: Mohd Yousif Khan "National Education Policy 2020- A Roadmap with Futuristic Vision" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-6 | Issue-2, February 2022, pp.1454-1457, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd49992.pdf

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have larger role to play in shaping their life and ensuring their complete development as a good human being. They must exhibit empathy and partake seriously by going to the grass root level and do an overhauling of the system wherever it is necessary to achieve the cause. Undoubtedly relevant education system and family upbringing can become the main game changer (Jain, 2020).

Structure of Education:

The new education policy is based on the 5 + 3 + 3 + 4 model corresponding to the age groups 3-8years (Foundational stage), 8-11 years (Preparatory Stage) 11-14 (Middle Stage) and 14-18 age groups in a major change from the 1986 policy that advocated for a 10 + 2 education system (Secondary Stage). This policy looks very flexible as far as choices are concerned. Students can learn a variety of subjects of their choice in a given timeframe. Provision of 4- year multidisciplinary program with multiple exists options is boon for the students. Choice Based Credit System is going to be the most catchy word of NEP 2020 for students who want all round development and multiple careers.

The Structure and Lengths of Degree Programmes:

In the context of the National Education Policy 2020 scheme, any undergraduate degree in any institution will be of duration of three or four years. One can leave the degree within this period. Any educational institution will have to give to the student a diploma degree after the student completes two years of study, a degree after the student completes three years of study and a certificate to those students who complete one year of study in any professional or vocational course of their choice. The Government of India will also help in establishing an Academic Bank of Credit for storing the academic scores digitally. This will enable the institutions to count the credit at the end and put it in the degree of the student. This will be helpful for those individuals who might have to leave the course mid-way. They can start the course later on from where they left off and not start from the beginning once again. Even though NEP 2020 says that Higher education institutions will be given the freedom to start PG courses there may be some difficulty in designing One Year PG Degree for students who have completed 4 Year UG Degree and a Two Year PG Degree for students who have completed 3 Year UG Degree.

New Education Policy 2020 Phase:

The phases of the new education policy are divided into four phases.

Foundation Stage- Foundation Stage of New Education Policy for 3 to 8 years children are included. This stage provides basic education which is flexible, multilevel, play-based, activity-based, and discovery based learning. The Foundation Stage has been fixed for 5 years. In which 3 years of pre-school education will be done in Anganwadi and class 1, 2 school education under which the languages skills and skill level of the students will be evaluated and focused in its development.

Preparatory Stage - The time of this stage is kept for 3 years. This stage consists of building on the play-, discovery-, and activity-based learning. This stage includes children from 8 to 11 years. In which he will have children up to class 5. In this stage of the new education policy, special attention will be focused on strengthening the numerical skills of the students and gradually introduces formal classroom learning with textbooks. At the same time, all children will also be given knowledge of the regional language. Along with this, children will be taught science, art, mathematics, etc. through experiments and prepare them to delve deeper into insights..

Middle Stage – The period of this stage has been fixed for 3 years. In This stage Children from 6th

grade to 8th grade have been included in which subject-based curriculum will be taught and coding will also be started from the children of 6th grade. At the same time, all the children will be given opportunities for vocational testing as well as vocational internship, whose aim is to make the children eligible for employment only during school education.

Secondary Stage- The period of this stage is 4 years. 9th grade in this stage Students from 12th standard is included. In this, intensive study of the subjects will be done. Within this stage, the educational curriculum of 8th to 12th standard courses has also been started and the alternative educational course has been started. Students can choose their subjects according to their choice, not within a specified stream. Under the new education policy, students have been given the freedom to choose subjects. Students can study the subjects of science as well as the subject of Arts or Kormas simultaneously. Due to the earlier 10 + 2 system, there was no pre-schooling in government schools. General from class 1 to 10 there was education and class 6 was a moist subject and there was freedom to choose subjects from class 6. Education used to start in the first 6 years, but now it will start in 3 years.

Board on students of 10th and 12th, keeping in mind the goal of development before the students the format of board examinations will also be changed to reduce the burden of examinations. Improvements such as a semester or multiple choice questions will be included. The examination will be conducted 2 times a year. There will be objective and subjective tests once a year. The main emphasis in the board examination will be on the test of knowledge so that the tendency of rote among students can be eliminated. From this point of view, this thinking of the government is welcome.

Research Stage:

Research stage consists of pursuing high quality research leading to a Ph.D. in any core subject, multidisciplinary subject, or interdisciplinary subject for a minimum period of three to four years for full-time and part-time study respectively. During Ph.D. they should undergo 8-credit coursework in teaching/ education/ pedagogy related to their chosen Ph.D. subject. The earlier one-year MPhil programme is discontinued.

More Holistic and Multidisciplinary Education:

The NEP 2020 claims that, a holistic and multidisciplinary education would aim to develop all capacities of human beings -intellectual, aesthetic, social, physical, emotional, and moral in an integrated manner. Such an education will help develop well-

rounded individuals that possess critical 21st century capacities in fields across the arts, humanities, languages, sciences, social sciences, and professional, technical, and vocational fields; an ethic of social engagement; soft skills, such as communication, discussion and debate; and rigorous specialization in a chosen field or fields. The NEP 2020 envisions one large multidisciplinary Higher Education Institution (HEI) in or near every district, by 2030.

Prominent areas of National Education Policy 2020:

- Transform the intent and content of Education Sector,
- Shift the burden of school bag to the Boon of learning,
- Less content and more Practical and integrated Learning (Integrated local with global)
- Holistic Learning and Analytical Thinking,
- Make youth future ready while focusing on National Goals,
- Critical Thinking and Inquiry Driven Learning,
- Ensure that students become Global Citizens while remaining connected to their roots,
- Shift focus from „what to think“ to „how to think“,
- Empower higher education institution through increased Autonomy,
- Emphasise on teacher training.

Suggestions:

- To execute policy effectively, there must be uniformity in the teaching and syllabus from class 5 to 12 level. It is seen that if students shift from state board in North to state board in South, they are face a lot of difficulties in studies due to difference in syllabus, curriculum and languages. Therefore, the syllabus should be uniform in the entire nation. For this a single Central Education Board for classes 5 to 12 may be established.
- Mandatory vocational education in schools from class 8 will boost Skill India program.
- All schools, colleges and universities should have a counselor to help students in coping with personal, social and career stress particularly, studies, examination, work and placement etc.
- Subject of Research Methodology may be included at undergraduate level itself for making researchers in the future.
- Since education is foundation for nation building and education policy is framed by the government, the effective implementation of the NEP- 2020 becomes necessary. Multiple exit options may result in vacant seats after every year. For instance, if 200 student taken admission

in first year, if 40 leave after one year with certificate due to some reasons, it will leave 160 students in second year. If another 50 leave after two years with Diploma, it will leave only 110 students in third year and many have less than 100 students in third year and may have less than 100 students in final year B.E, if few more leave after third year. Then what about those vacant seats?

- Autonomy should be provided to all higher educational institutes.
- Considering technological challenges in future and to attract brilliant students at the early age in field of researcher and development exclusive research Universities to be establishment in each state.
- In addition to educational institutions, sports schools may be opened that can help students i all round development.
- Simultaneously, NCC, NSS, extra-curricular, and co-curricular activities, hobby classes, do-it-yourself projects, best from waste, drawing and painting, gardening etc. will help to develop creativity and interest in students.
- Students may be encouraged to set-up small personal laboratories in their houses with the help of school. This will help them a lot to understand many basic facts in science and which may boost their creativity.
- For the effective implementation of the policy there must be only two bodies such as “Board of school education” and “Board of College education” which can provide detailed roadmap. Academicians, educationists, and expert from various bodies may be part of such board.

Conclusion:

NEP-2020 with its primary focus on access, equity quality, affordability and accountability is aiming to ensure that Indian students become global citizens while remaining connected to their roots. It encompasses provision for better learning and employment outcomes of the younger generation through various initiatives and target set forth in the policy. However, the success of this policy depends largely upon the implementation as well as the seriousness of effort of the stakeholders. The budgetary allocations are meaningless unless accompanied by proper planning and execution of the key aspects of the policy. The clear roles and responsibilities articulated in the form of action points for the HEIs, state government and central government hold the key to the success of these

transformational initiatives, to transform India into a vibrant knowledge society and global knowledge superpower by making both school and college education more holistic, flexible, multidisciplinary suited to 21st century needs and brings out the unique capabilities of each students.

Reference

- [1] GoI (2020). National Education Policy -2020, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India.
- [2] Hindustantimes.com, Edited by Nandini (2020). New education Policy 2020 Highlights: School and Higher Education to see Major Changes. Hindustan Times. <https://www.hindustantimes.com/education/new-education-policy-2020-lives-updates>
- [3] Jain, S. (2020). The National education policy 2020: *A policy for the Times* UNESCO (2017). Education for Sustainable Development Goals: learning objectives. <https://unesdoc.Unesco.org/ark:>

